

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NWAKWUE****FIRST NAME: JOSEPH****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Writing a good essay (EUCLID 2019, 1 – 4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5 - 13)
3. Paper writing rules of thumb (EUCLID 2019, 14)
4. Literature Review (EUCLID 2019, 17)
5. Writing style guide (EUCLID 2019, 24)
6. Difference between British and American English (EUCLID 2019, 27)
7. CMS Formatting (EUCLID 2019, 44)

GOOD ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Communication is so critical in our personal and professional life as it enables us to be able to convey our beliefs, ideas, thoughts or needs with clarity to other parties. It facilitates consensus building, alignment and teamwork while avoiding confusion and miss-understanding. Ineffective communication impact negatively on our personal as well as professional life. The ACA-401D coursepack and the online video by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck which is the basis for this RP, gave a fairly detailed review of essays, a key communication tool. It covered their structure, do and don'ts, and tips on how to write a good essay. A six-step process for writing a great essay starting from defining the question, analyzing the task and developing an initial plan, researching the topic, organizing your ideas, writing the essay, referencing the essay and editing the essay were very clearly laid out. I found the materials very insightful and an excellent guide for my future writings.

2) **GOOD ESSAY WRITING**

Essays are an important medium for communication be it technical, commercial, business, or social, especially in the academic community. Baden Eunson (Communicating in the 21st Century 2005, 225) captured it as follows:

Essays are documents on specific topics that contain a mix of fact and opinion, laid out in logical sequences and employing appropriate strategies of expression. An essay comprises both content (what is said) and form (the way in which it is said). These aspects are separate, but not unrelated.

A good essay must therefore comprise of two related parts – form and content. The form deals with the structure, style, and presentation of the essay while the content is primarily the message. Put differently, the form answers the “how” question while the content answers the “what” question. A good essay accurately interprets evidence and draws reasonable conclusions therefrom, identifies the salient arguments for and against the thesis, thoughtfully evaluates alternative points of view, uses, and cites all relevant source material, presents ideas in a coherent, clear and technically correct manner.

a) Essay Writing Rules of Thumb

Writing a good essay requires discipline and focus. Since the main purpose of an essay is to communicate a position or idea, the essay must be clear, coherent, focused, and uses language that can be understood on the first read. The ACA-401D course material laid out a series of rules to help in achieving these objectives. The main thesis or argument of the essay must be clearly and well spelt out, the essay must stay focused on the issues of relevance to the thesis, research your topic extensively, your writing should be clear, unambiguous and in simple language, your views and positions should be evidence based and be sure to define the right boundaries, avoiding over generalization. Painstakingly proof-read and review your work to ensure correctness and that you did not plagiarize someone’s work. It is also a good practice to have your colleague or friend review the work and provide feedback before you finalize your essay.

b) Plagiarism

In writing essays, plagiarism, which is “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2019, 5) should be avoided. Put differently, plagiarism is the stealing of someone’s work, a very unethical and serious academic offence with significant consequences. According to Roka (Yam Bahadur Roka, 2017), plagiarism is a “common but avoidable” problem, listing ten different types of plagiarism and made useful suggestions on how to avoid it. To avoid plagiarism, all sources of information need to be cited and the various citation techniques, paraphrases, signal phrases and referencing rules were duly explained.

c) Punctuation and Choice of English

I found the emphasis on proper use of punctuation to separate written sentences and parts of sentences, and to make their meaning clear very useful. It is clear from the course material that this is very important in conveying the message exactly as intended, as improper use of punctuations could distort the message and lead to miss-communication. Equally important, is the use of correct grammar. The choice of words and how they are used are vital in conveying the intention of the author. Care therefore is required in ensuring a consistent use of either the American or British English in any work to avoid confusing the reader.

i) *Punctuation and Syntax*

Punctuation marks are a set of symbols with specific rules for the usage of each one to guides you on how to read a sentence by simplifying and clarifying ideas and making text easier to read and understand while syntax is the arrangement of words in a sentence. While both serve similar functions, they are however not the same thing, and neither one can replace the other. A proper understanding and use of these tools are required and indeed very important in writing a good essay that delivers the message as intended. Improper punctuation and syntax could mar an essay and convey the wrong message.

ii) *British vs. American English*

For someone like me whose education was based on British English but have had the opportunity of living and working in America, the difference between English and British English can be confusing. There are differences in pronunciations, punctuation, spelling, grammar, syntax, date format and even jargons and obscenities. It is very important to understand these and stay consistent with the chosen English to avoid confusing the reader.

d) Style Guide

The use and importance of a writing style guide to ensure consistency and coherence especially for specialized writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting, or where there are many contributing authors for a publication was a new discovery for me. The Chicago Writing style (Turabian) and American English were recommended even as other styles will be acceptable. A style guide defined as “a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent” (EUCLID 2019, 24) is therefore a good tool to ensure consistency, adapt your writing to specific client requirement and save some editing or proof-reading time.

e) Chicago Style Formatting

The Chicago Manual of Style is a compilation of formatting, referencing, and citing rules applied to works written in American English (mostly) and published in historical or social sciences journals. The manual was created by the University of Chicago Press and the first version was released in 1906. Currently, at the time of this writing, it is on its 17th edition ([Chicago Style Format. The Chicago Manual of Style in short| EssayPro](#)).

Kate Turabian adapted and simplified the CMOS for students and researchers, a version presently named the “Turabian.” The Turabian style is the recommended formatting style for research writing by EUCLID. It details formatting standards covering all aspects of the essay from abbreviations, acronyms, capitalization, end notes and footnotes, numbers and dates, headings and lists, italics and quotes, bibliography, and tables and many more.

3) CONCLUSION

It is clear from this study that communication through essays is critical to our everyday personal and professional life. It is therefore very important that one adapts a writing style that is simple, well structured, with appropriate style and correct grammar. The use of “plain language principles” (EUCLID 2019, 56) was recommended. Good essay writing therefore is an art that requires due attention to details and ranges from, analyzing the task and developing a plan, researching the topic, organizing your ideas, writing the essay, referencing the essay, and editing the essay, avoiding plagiarism, using correct grammar, appropriate essay structure, punctuation, and style, while ensuring use of right and simple, easy to understand words, short sentences and paragraphs to convey exactly the intended message.

The key concepts I took away from the materials are the basic rules of essay writing, the dangers of plagiarism, importance of proper punctuation, need for and use of a writing style guide, differences between British and American English, use of the Chicago style of formatting and English translation of commonly used Latin words. To be able to write good essays therefore, one must be familiar and conversant with the key concepts highlighted in the course material and consistently apply them.

I found this course material and exercises very useful and helpful and look forward to improving my writing as I deploy these tools.

REFERENCES

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